

Pelargonium echinatum Prickly-stemmed pelargonium

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PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 66.57 Gigabases
Approximate N50: 16.39 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm
Genome Length: 0.57 Gigabases
BUSCO completeness score:
99.8% [Single: 89.9%, Duplicated: 9.9%]
BUSCO database: viridiplantae
Assembly N50: 48 987.56 kilobases
Contig number: 1 473

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Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

Group: Eudicot

Size: 0.3 - 0.5 m

Distribution:

This species is endemic and widespread across western South Africa, from the Richtersveld to Clanwilliam.

Importance:

Prickly-stemmed pelargonium is among the most beautiful winter-flowering pelargoniums. Traditionally, South African tribes have used Pelargonium species to treat ailments such as diarrhea, dysentery, wounds, fever, colds, sore throats, and urinary issues, to name a few. The essential oil from Pelargonium species is highly valued for its rose-like fragrance with minty notes, widely used in perfumery and aromatherapy. Known for its calming and balancing properties, it helps relieve anxiety, fatigue, and depression, while also benefiting skin care and respiratory health.

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